

IN-HABIT - INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies

D8.9 IN-HABIT VIDEO IN CORDOBA

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VERSION HISTORY

Version	Status	Date	Contributor/partner	Summary of changes
V 0.1	Draft	26/08/2023	C. Marrone, S. Marrone, E. Cianchi (BOT)	Advanced draft
V 0.2	Draft	28/08/2023	BOT	Reviewed draft
V 0.3	Final document	30/08/2023	BOT	Language final revision

LIST OF ACRONYMS

D	Deliverable
DECO	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication & Outreach
DC	Dissemination & Communication
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union

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GA	Grant Agreement
GDEI	Gender, Diversity, Equity, Inclusion
H2020	Horizon 2020 projects
IHW	Inclusive Health and Well-being
KLC	Key Local Contact
LCA	Local Community Activator
PC	Project Coordinator
PP	Project Partner
SMSCs	Small and medium-sized cities
T	Task
WP	Work Package

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Deliverable description

This document outlines the development of the INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies (IN-HABIT) video for the city of Cordoba – WP8 Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach (DECO) strategy – deliverable D8.9 of task 8.2 (communication and engagement actions and tools).

Description, according to Grant Agreement: Videos: 4 short web videos will be produced when hard VIS are co-deployed [...] to present the project achievements using easy-to-understand animations and infographics. The videos will be accessible via the website, distributed via social media and other sector-related communication portals and platforms, and will also be used at events to present the project. They will have an emotional component and will feature keynote speakers on the tasks and innovations to promote IHW achieved in each city, opinions from citizens, and footage of children and other key community representatives.

The outcome is four videos about the project and its positive impacts on the Lucca, Nitra, Riga and Cordoba IN-HUBs and environment in general, available at the following link: <https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/media-press/>.

The ultimate goal is to produce dynamic, user-friendly, and easy-to-understand content to enhance public awareness and promote local innovations and spaces, through a recognisable and strong visual identity based on the project's communication guidelines.

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1.2 Technical features

The videos have been created using professional skills and involving professional video makers. Images were shot in full HD 1920 x 1080 resolution, with the footage representing a good 80% of the videos, and stock footage material used only when necessary.

BOT has relied on local video operators, cooperating closely to identify valuable resources and discuss the most representative local implementations, achievements, and available data in order to give the most comprehensive idea of the above and have a direct connection with the territories and local innovations depicted, as well as enhancing the professionalism of the videos.

A professional interpreter has taken care of the voice over, and the right pronunciation of wording in local languages, as well as the subtitles, have been carefully reviewed by relying on local contacts, namely the cities' KLCs and LCAs.

2. PRODUCTION PROCESS

2.1 Conceptual phase and visuals

The IN-HABIT promotional video has been defined and confirmed and comprises two parts: general promotional video and local spotlight videos.

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The structure of the videos and their production calendar has been shared and co-designed with local partners.

Structure: Introduction (general part - 1.5 min.) + Local highlights (local part - 3.5 min.)

General part: celebrative, institutional, explaining the project and its potential. Giving context of the network, why is it important to share possible impact, and replicability features.

Including animated infographics about project data.

+

Local part: celebrating achievements, “in the field” work and innovation, focus on human challenges and success, to be shot in the field to communicate successful initiatives and show places and population.

Interviews both with institutional representatives and key community representatives, ideally showing events/proceedings and if possible local data (qualitative and quantitative), if available.

The general aim of the promotional video is to communicate the project identity and convey its core messages through the use of a dynamic, attention-grabbing description of the actions, while at the same time conveying important contextual information through graphics that adhere to the visual identity and through selected icons, imagery, and 2D animations. The use of carefully selected imagery helps viewers to better understand the reach of the project and its main actions in a specific, effective way.

The project’s visual identity has been incorporated in the videos through the use of icons, a distinctive trait of the project’s visuals. The icons allow immediate communication and a friendly, easy-to-use interface.

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Infographics and 2D animation have also been utilised in order to include complex information in simpler representations, and to convey project information wherever available. Finally, the result was to offer a friendlier, immediate, and dynamic approach.

2.2. Production timing & storytelling format

Starting from M29, a discussion was opened up with Project Partners in order to convey the existing achievements and the protagonists of the IN-HUBs' testimonies in powerful, interesting tools. These videos would have the purpose of promoting the project and its progress in all four cities, acting as both a storytelling tool and a dissemination tool at the same time. This option would allow Key Local Contacts (KLCs) and Local Community Activators (LCAs), along with all the local partners and population involved in the project, to better communicate the cities' highlights and innovations, from a local perspective. Feedback from Project Partners was carefully collected and requested amends applied accordingly.

After the confirmation and development of the visual identity of the project in M6, and following a co-design process with the Project Partners (PPs), in particular local ones, the first release of the videos will take place in M36 for the cities of Lucca, Nitra, and Riga, while the video production in Cordoba has been postponed to autumn 2023, when the hard VIS in the city will be more advanced and the video more effective in showing the impact in the city.

However, another video was produced for Cordoba, depicting the first 30 months of the project, and made available by the local team, in order to spread the word and give the correct information and importance to the activities held. It can be found at the following link:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KdztXniLGwk>

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Updates on D. 8.9. Cordoba IN-HABIT Video will follow accordingly.

Length ranges from 4 to 6 minutes per video.

Given that inclusiveness is one of IN-HABIT’s guiding values both in internal and external communication, following a GDEI approach, careful thought was put into the representation of images, taking into account the characteristics and the social/cultural features of different cultures. BOT also ensured that the language used for the communication was accessible to non-experts, avoiding any reference to EU jargon and technical terms.

Finally, local social media channels and contact information were shared in order to have a central role in reaching out to groups of categories and collectives at risk of exclusion.

2.3. Editing and finalising

General and local scripts, along with the accompanying suitable imagery and wording, were carefully written and analysed with corresponding partners with a shared roadmap, and continuous updating along the production and post-production process, as points of verification with the IN-HUB local representatives, was conducted.

The script of the **general promotional video** is as follows:

Table 1 - Screenplay of the general part

GENERAL PART		
Subtitles	Typography	Visuals

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	INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies	IN-HABIT logo
IN-HABIT is working to foster inclusive health and well-being in Cordoba, Riga, Lucca, and Nitra by combining technological, digital, nature-based, cultural, and social innovations in urban public spaces.	Inclusive health and well-being Technological Digital Nature-based Cultural Social	Use the map from the main project video created showing the cities. Footage of some of the spaces and the innovations deployed in them. And/or icons representing each of the innovations listed.
The impact of these solutions on health and well-being at a city level will be monitored and assessed.	Impact Monitored and assessed	Footage depicting potential impact
The data generated and knowledge developed will be made available for everyone, everywhere, enabling other cities to replicate the successful solutions and their positive results.	Available for everyone, everywhere Replicate	Visual showing the knowledge spreading to other cities around the world.
Halfway through the project, IN-HABIT has been		
setting up IN-HUBs; launching an online business incubation programme; developing behavioural games;	IN-HUBs Business incubation programme Behavioural games	Footage of the activities or an infographic showing the activities listed.

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<p>creating an IN-HABIT app;</p> <p>initiating projects using the Design for Change methodology;</p> <p>implementing communication and dissemination activities;</p> <p>and cooperating with sister projects on clustering activities.</p>	<p>IN-HABIT app</p> <p>Design for Change methodology</p> <p>Communication and dissemination</p> <p>Clustering activities</p>	
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Language

Four videos with English voiceover over the whole video, subtitled in local languages and with original language statements (quotes from local people) subtitled in English, were chosen as a more effective and spontaneous means of communication, while giving the opportunity to boost impact, being more institutional and also understandable locally at the same time.

In particular, for the local videos, after an internal discussion with the PPs, English was maintained as the video language for the voiceover, to allow the dissemination of local actions to wider audiences, while subtitles were added and checked in the four local languages of the project (Spanish, Italian, Latvian, Slovak).

When it came to the interviews, it was agreed those would be kept in local language to allow more spontaneous, effective communication to the public by collecting testimonies and points of view from representatives directly involved in the project, locally and at various levels (IN-HUB participants, institutional representatives, project partners, and so on).

The scripts of the **four local parts** are available upon request. Scripts and voiceover have once again been carefully written by BOT and translated and reviewed by local teams in a co-design approach, as well as the selection of the most appropriate places and activities to shoot, and the decision about the local interviews, which were entirely up to the cities' representatives. Wherever possible, shooting took place during other, already scheduled activities (Site visit in Riga, Animal area inauguration in Lucca...) in order to optimise the efforts of the local teams, and also to give a better idea of the actual activities going on during the project lifetime and beyond.

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The general video (English teaser) and four local ones all end with a final slide with logos of the IN-HABIT organisations, credits, and a call to action to learn more about the project and follow its further development in the future.

The broadness of the project innovations, the amplitude of the outreach, the idea of - generally speaking - hard and soft VIS and their deployment, together with a concrete impact in the inhabitants' lives, were the guiding principles for storytelling. Above all, replicable and relatable solutions such as the ones developed in our four pilot cities were the centre of the narrative, together with giving importance and underlying the specificities of each city through an emotional storytelling based on the interviews with the protagonists of the stories.

A series of data, conveyed through infographics, represented the actual impact of the project halfway through its life, and the open possibility of generating new opportunities, collaborations, and spaces for inhabitants, along with allowing them to be the voice of their neighbourhoods, in an open, friendly way.

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3. RELEASES

As previously mentioned, the releases have followed a co-design process with the partners, both for the general and local videos, working closely on identifying the most relevant information to communicate. Improvements to the script and voiceover were included where requested. The local videos were finally finalised in M36, following an accurate review process by the local partners, and published on the project website:<https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/>

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